

Identifying religion's impact on HIV service provision with stigmatized groups and developing models that draw on religion's positive contributions

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Executive Summary

The U.S. President's Emergency Plan for AIDS Research (PEPFAR) named four key populations – men who have sex with men, sex workers, people who inject drugs, and young women – as the focus of continued global response to HIV/AIDS. In Kenya, key populations face a high burden of HIV, but encounter barriers to HIV prevention and treatment due to social, religious, legal and political forces. In this context, PEPFAR relies upon faith-based organizations (FBOs) as the largest non-governmental providers of HIV services as central to effective and sustained HIV prevention, treatment and support services. However, little is known about the role of religion in addressing the stigma and discrimination faced by key populations.

We employed qualitative methods informed by the principles of Grounded Theory to understand the role of religion on stigma and access to HIV services for key populations in Kenya. Kenyan researchers conducted key informant interviews (KII) and focus group discussions (FGD) with FBO staff and members of key populations across six counties (Eldoret, Kiambu, Kilifi, Kisumu, Mombasa and Nairobi). There were 190 participants across all interviews and focus group discussions. Interviews were conducted in English and Swahili and all data was transcribed in English for analysis. Data were coded with a combination of inductive and deductive codes. Coded data was analyzed to compare the experiences of key populations, religious groups, and to explore regional differences. Codes were grouped into categories and mapped into a conceptual model to explain the role religion has on stigma, discrimination, and access to HIV prevention and treatment services among key populations.

We found religion plays an important role in facilitating access to HIV services and reducing stigma, while also influencing stigma and discrimination. Religion emerged in the form of beliefs, practices,

religious organizations and structures, the influence of religion in broader society, and the role of religion in fighting stigma. The majority of participants were Christian (90%) and some were Muslim (10%), and they all professed varied beliefs. Individual beliefs described by key populations and FBO staff expressed sources of discrimination (e.g., homosexuality and adultery are sins), coping with stigma (“only God can pass judgement”) and acceptance for key populations (“all sins are equal”, “God created everyone in His own image”). The multiple forms of religion (agency and power, organizational structure of religious communities, beliefs and practices, relationship to secular to society) intersected with several themes, and were also facilitators of both stigma and discrimination and access to HIV services. The figure below shows the ways in which each form of religion can both influence stigma and discrimination and increase access to HIV services.

Religion plays multiple roles in reducing and contributing to stigma and discrimination and in facilitating access to HIV services for key populations. FBOs that successfully reach key populations have staff that are motivated and trained to work with key populations and involve the key populations in conducting peer education and outreach. They also partner with like-minded organizations and refer clients to trusted services, share resources, and participate in larger networks or bodies with a shared mission. However, these FBOs are challenged by high staff turnover, lack of funding, limited services, and threats from “religious zealots” in the broader community who disapprove of their work.

Key populations have varied experiences with FBOs, showing that there is not consistency in the services provided by FBOs. Stigma and discrimination, such as being turned away from services, forced disclosure, or lack of confidentiality at health services, is not limited to FBOs and was described as being a problem for PWID, MSM and SWs at public health facilities as well. Drop-in centers and other targeted services for KPs were preferred and may be an important partner for referral and sensitization of FBO staff. In addition to the role of religion in accessing services, religion also influences coping with stigma among some members of the key populations, particularly PWID, MSM and SWs. Leveraging the interpretation and beliefs of these key populations as a method of sensitization for faith leaders may be effective in reducing stigma within places of worship and health facilities. There is a need for future research on the faith-based interventions that use the strengths of religion for psychosocial support and coping with stigma. In addition, there is greater need to explore faith-based service provision in Kenya for HIV services to understand the gaps between the perceptions of key populations of services at FBOs and the FBOs mission of providing services to key populations.

Introduction

This report details the qualitative research conducted by Emory University (Atlanta, GA) and St. Paul University (Limuru, Kenya) to assess the influence of religion on HIV prevention, treatment, and support for members of key populations. The study was part of a joint initiative between UNAIDS and PEPFAR to strengthen collaboration with faith-based organizations. The report includes: background information on the partners and research question; research methodology; findings from focus group discussions and interviews; and recommendations.

Background

Partnership

From 2008-2015, the Interfaith Health Program (IHP), Rollins School of Public Health, Emory University, carried out projects designed to strengthen collaboration between faith-based organizations (FBOs) and programs with the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) and President's Emergency Plan for AIDS Relief (PEPFAR). In July 2016, IHP and Saint Paul's University (SPU) of Kenya began work on the PEPFAR/UNAIDS Joint Initiative to Strengthen Collaborations with Faith-Based Organizations. As part of the initiative, IHP and SPU sought to understand religion's influence on stigma/discrimination and access to HIV services for key populations in Kenya and those core elements that allow FBOs to carry out effective HIV services with key populations.

Country context

In Kenya, it is estimated that 1.6 million people are living with HIV, and in 2016, 62,000 people became newly infected with the disease; however, key populations account for almost one-third of new infections (sex workers 14%, men who have sex with men, 15%; and people who inject drugs, 3.8%) (UNAIDS 2017, NACC 2014). Confronting social stigma, punitive legal systems, and judgement from care providers, key populations (people who inject drugs [PWID], men who have sex with men [MSM], and sex workers [SWs], mature minors), often face barriers to effective prevention, treatment, and support programs to address their particular needs and priorities. The HIV prevalence data for these communities are often incomplete, despite these gaps, the data on HIV prevalence in Kenya for MSM, SWs, and PWID demonstrate the scope of the epidemic and the impact of HIV disease on the women and men in these communities (Beyrer, Baral, Grievenson, Goodreau, Chariyalerstsak, *et. al.*, 2012).

HIV/AIDS: Religion and Stigma

Religion, and religious leaders, hold a position of authority in Kenyan communities. Nonetheless, while FBOs have been "critical" in responding to the HIV epidemic in Sub-Saharan Africa, there is less scholarship on how FBOs have or have not contributed to reducing stigma (Keikelame, 2010). Religious doctrines and the messages perpetuated by religious leaders often convey the message that those infected with HIV have committed sins and therefore are justified in having such "punishment." These messages further stigmatize people with HIV/AIDS (Otolok-Tanga E., 2007). At the same time, religious leaders have the ability to fight stigma and discrimination against people living with or affected by HIV, and many have proven effective at this (Otolok-Tanga E., 2007). These two roles related to stigma are held in tension in each of the major religious groups in Kenya—Christian (82.5% total: 47.7% Protestant, 23.3% Catholic) and Muslim (11.1%) (Central Intelligence Agency, 2015). Stigmatizing attitudes among religious people is "value expressive, or symbolic...which occurs when the core behavioral and moral values of a dominant group are threatened" (Miller, 2011). Therefore, by blaming people who acquire

HIV for their own behavior, the uninfected feel they remain firmly part of the “in-group” (Miller, 2011). When HIV is associated with moral blame, it then often acts as a deterrent for disclosure (Keikelame, 2010).

According to the work of Memoona Hasnain, stigma against HIV/AIDS is more pronounced in Muslim majority countries (Hasnain, 2005). While Muslims in Kenya are not the majority, there are areas and communities that are primarily Muslim. In “Islam and AIDS: Between Scorn, Pity and Justice” edited by Farid Esack and Sarah Chiddy (2009), multiple authors describe the various streams of thought in the Islamic discourse on HIV/AIDS and how they might further either stigma or compassion. For example, Hashim Kamali discusses the determinist stream of Malik Badri, which sees AIDS as “a sign on divine justice towards homosexuals and others who disobeyed God’s limits.” For him, the “only remedy for everyone is to adhere to Islamic values.” In contrast, Kamali advocates for a “Theology of Compassion” based on general Shari’ah principles which include “protection of basic human values, and the mustering of communal resources to prevent individuals from being stigmatized” (Esack & Chiddy, 2010).

Theological foundation

This project reflects theological assumptions articulated by certain movements in both the Christian and Islamic traditions. While the specific frameworks within each religion are distinctive, both movements support the idea that members of key populations communities are best equipped to describe for themselves the influences of religion in their own lives. Such an idea is grounded in the assumption that members of key populations communities have a legitimate perspective to share regarding their own experiences of religious belief and practice. Those perspectives should be taken seriously and, in fact, should be given priority over the perspectives of others who might have very strong opinions about key populations communities.

Such an idea is theologically supported in the Christian tradition by a movement known as liberation theology and in the Islamic tradition by the concepts of fitrah and khilafah. The movement of liberation theology in the Christian tradition is grounded in the core claim that God takes the side of the poor . In practice, this theological claim means that those who are poor are best equipped to describe their experiences of God in the context of social-structural forces that create and sustain economic inequities and disparities. Liberation theology assumes that religious faith and practice reflect God’s intention for humanity when they support efforts to reduce economic disparities and build economic equity. Conversely, religious faith and practice fail to reflect God’s intention when they fail to address such disparities.

The concept of God’s preferential option for the poor originated through discussions held among groups of Christians in Latin America. These groups were called base communities and they were comprised in large part by laypeople with few economic resources. Reflecting on their own faith, the members of these base communities emphasized God’s solidarity with those who faced economic injustices— injustices faced by many of the members themselves. The phrase was introduced in academic theological writing through the work of the Roman Catholic Dominican priest and philosopher, Gustavo Gutierrez in his book *A Theology of Liberation: History, Politics, Salvation* (1971).

Other theologians subsequently expanded the concept to describe God’s active work in the liberation of those who faced oppression of various sorts. Marcella Althaus-Reid, a theologian from Argentina, expanded this idea to include sex workers and LGBTQ people. Althaus-Reid demonstrated that both

groups faced stigmatization and acts of physical and sexual violence. She then argued that liberation theology teaches that God stands with those who face such stigma and violence and is actively working to bring about justice. Althaus-Reid argued that liberation theology must extend its thinking, its practices, and its commitments to claim that God displays a preferential option for all people who are condemned or despised by those in power; while this option extends to those who are poor, it also extends to many others, including same gender loving people and sex workers, even if some religious authorities wanted to limit the concept to the poor alone. Althaus-Reid writes (2007b, 27):

“Liberation theology did not set out chairs for poor women, or poor gays—or at least it never did so willingly. The inclusive project affirmed itself by exclusion policies which determined the identity of the poor. The poor who were included were conceived of as male, generally peasant, vaguely indigenous, Christian and heterosexual. In fact, militant churches would not have needed many chairs around the table of the Lord if these criteria had been applied. It describes the identity of a minority of the poor. The poor in Latin America can not be stereotyped so easily and they include poor women, transvestites in poor street neighbourhoods and gays everywhere.”

For Althaus-Reid, the failure of liberation theology to truly open the Lord’s table to all means that the movement has had little theological imagination to understand how God acts in the world in communion with any who face oppression or violence. God’s preferential option does not extend merely to the image of the poor as envisioned by bishops or priests or moral theologians; rather, God’s preferential option extends in messy, multiple ways into social networks and social structures that justify violence in the name of politics or the marketplace or even in defense of the faith. For Althaus-Reid, this messy, multiple expression of God’s preferential option is the very definition of grace and it does not flow only through approved channels to be received only by people deemed worthy by those in power.

While liberation theology supports an assumption of this research that members of key populations are best equipped to describe the influences of religion in their lives, that assumption is also supported within Islam by the concepts of fitrah and khilafah

Fitrah refers to the idea that human nature is innately inclined to do the right and toward virtue. This principle recognizes an inherent goodness, worth, and dignity in each human being. Islam also teaches that reason is a distinguishing characteristic of human beings and so we possess the capacity to make rational choices reflective of the good. Of course, human beings may not follow the good. We may deny the truth or we may fail in our responsibility to reflect and help bring to fruition God’s intention for the creation. Human beings have an obligation to carry out this responsibility by being good stewards of the resources God has given us; this obligation remains even if we refuse to accept. This idea of stewardship and our agency to accept or refuse is known as khilafah.

Together, Khilafah and fitrah imply that both human motivations and the social-structural factors that contribute to our experiences in life are complex. If our human nature is not fundamentally corrupted by sin but pure (fitrah) and if we have an obligation to support God’s intention for the creation (khilafah) then we cannot dismiss the lives and daily actions of members of key populations communities as automatically worthy of our condemnation. Their nature reflects fitrah and their efforts to practice khilafah cannot be dismissed. In fact, they may have a particular revelation of God’s intention in the context of their own communities.

In summary, this study assumes that members of key populations communities are well aware of the influences of religion in their own lives and can describe the ways in which such influences may contribute to their health or may lead to threats or actual instances of violence and rejection. This assumption mirrors the claims of the liberation theology movement in Christianity and is supported by the concepts of fitrah and khilafah in Islam.

Methods

Research team

Investigators from Saint Paul University and Emory University led the research team. The research team for data collection and analysis was composed of Kenyans who had experience interacting with key populations. The team was trained in qualitative methods and research ethics. This research was approved by the Amref Ethics and Scientific Review Committee in Kenya and Emory University Institutional Review Board.

Methodology

The goal of this project was to assess the influence of religion on HIV prevention, treatment, and support program for members of key populations, as these groups have high prevalence rates and because social, religious, legal, and political forces in many parts of the globe contribute to barriers to HIV prevention and treatment for these groups. Our research addressed three objectives:

1. To gain knowledge on the effects of religion in relation to cultural norms, laws/policies, and barriers to HIV services in relation to key populations.
2. To identify the common elements that exist among faith-based organizations and faith-based health systems (FBOs/FBHSs) that provide effective HIV services to one or more of the named groups.
3. To utilize the knowledge gained about these elements to design a curriculum to be used with FBOs/FBHSs to improve their services with the named groups and increase their capacity to carry out such work.

We selected a qualitative approach informed by the principles of Grounded Theory to explore the effects of religion and the common elements of faith-based organizations through lived experiences among key populations and FBOs in Kenya. Through key-informant interviews (KIIs) and focus group discussions (FGDs), we sought to understand the role of religion on access to HIV services from the perspective of mature minors, men who have sex with men, people who inject drugs and female sex workers. We also captured the experiences of faith-based organizations who serve key populations through KIIs to learn how they provide effective HIV services.

Data collection

Data was collected through KIIs and FGDs in six counties in Kenya: Uasin-Gishu, Kiambu, Kilifi, Kisumu, Mombasa and Nairobi. We prioritized these counties based on 1) HIV incidence, 2) access to gatekeepers, 3) organized key populations communities and/or 4) the presence of FBOs.

Interviews and focus groups followed a semi-structured guide of key topics that included

- accessing health services and trusted service providers
- experiences with FBOs
- experiences with stigma
- perceptions of religion

Data was collected in English and Swahili, as determined by participants. KIIs and FGDs were audio recorded and later transcribed into English for data analysis.

Table 1 shows how data was collected among each group and the total number of participants from each group.

Table 1. Data Collection by Key Population

Group	Data collection method	Count	Number of Participants
FBOs	KII	5	5
Mature minors	FGD	4	42
Men who have sex with men	FGD	4	42
	KII	5	5
People who inject drugs	FGD	4	30
	KII	4	4
Female sex workers	FGD	6	61
	KII	1	1
Total		33	190

Recruitment

We used purposive sampling to select participants. The criteria for participation among key population participants included:

- Living in one of the six counties
- Self- identify as MSM, PWID, MM, and/or SW

For FBOs, we included participants who met the following criteria:

- Leader of an FBO serving key populations in one of the six counties *or* An FBO staff member who provides direct services to key populations in one of the six counties

We identified participants through gatekeepers within local networks, including NGOs and FBOs, and among key population members. The recruitment included consultations and clarifications of the goals of the research with gatekeepers and participants. Only participants who provided written consent were included in the study. To protect the identify of participants, all participants were assigned a participant ID and transcripts were de-identified. Participants were recruited for variation by region, gender, religion, and key population group. In total, there were 190 participants across all interviews and focus group discussions. The demographic characteristics of participants were as follows:

Table 2. Participant Characteristics

Participant Characteristics	Count
Gender	
Male	96
Female	94
Religion	
Christian	147
Muslim	38
Atheist	1
County	
Kiambu	34
Kilifi	40
Kisumu	31
Mombasa	39
Nairobi	23
Uasin-Gishu	23
Age	
Under 18	15
18-24	72
25-34	77
35-44	22
45-54	3
55 or older	1

Data Analysis Procedures

Kenyan researchers conducted data analysis by reviewing transcripts to identify themes to develop a codebook of inductive codes and deductive codes. Then, transcripts were coded and the codes were analyzed to describe and compare the experiences across different key populations, religious groups, and regions. Themes were grouped into categories and mapped into a conceptual model to explain the role religion on stigma and discrimination and access to HIV prevention and treatment services among key populations.

Findings

Most participants discussed their relationship to religion and its influence in their lives; however, mature minors focused more of their discussion on the stigma of living with HIV and access to services than on religion. FBOs who participated echoed these experiences based on their work with key populations and expressed challenges and facilitators of providing services to key populations.

While there were many differences between the lived experiences of men who have sex with men, mature minors, sex workers and people who inject drugs, several common themes emerged among them. For example, participants raised issues of disclosure, lack of sensitization and stigmatizing cultural perceptions as factors that led to stigma and discrimination. At the same time, participants described several factors led to increased access to HIV prevention and treatment services, such as self-actualization, peer support, targeted support from health service providers, supportive religious teachings, and advocacy. These themes each interacted with religion in distinct ways, which we conceptualized into four categories: 1) agency and power, 2) beliefs and practices, 3) organizational structure of religious communities, 4) relationship of religion to broader to society. The interaction between religion and factors that lead to stigma and discrimination and facilitators of HIV prevention and treatment services are shown in the below conceptual model and described in detail in the following sections.

First, we present findings on general experiences of stigma and discrimination among each of the key population to highlight distinctions and similarities between the groups in the context of Kenya. Then, we present on how religion influences stigma and discrimination and health access overall.

Experiences of Stigma and Discrimination Faced by Key Populations

Among the key populations, participants described experiences of stigma and discrimination in their daily lives, including in religious and health care settings. Discrimination in the context of this study is the unjust treatment of key populations by family, community, religious leaders, or health care providers. Almost every member of key pops described experience with some form of discrimination in multiple facets of their daily life, including within their family, in religious settings, and within health facilities.

MSM

MSM participants gave many examples of discrimination. In general, they experienced discrimination from members of the community by being cast aside by their families, denied leadership positions and being evicted from their homes. Some said they were the target of insults and ridicule within their communities and were hindered from living their own lives without fear.

MSM described discrimination at health facilities in the form of judgement and negative attitudes from health service providers, particularly at public health facilities. There were instances where people were received poor service or denied service completely.

They often described experiencing discrimination within religious settings due to Christians and Muslim beliefs. According to participants, homosexuality is contrary to the teachings of the Bible and the Qur'an, so the MSM were discriminated in the mosques and churches with the added threat of violence even at home by religious zealots. MSM pastors and their ministry were also discriminated by faith leaders. Their approach was not accepted by fellow faith leaders who judged them for being MSM.

PWID

PWID were also victims of discrimination due to their use of drugs, the economic cost of their drug use, and other actions associated with their drug use. They stated that PWID are cast out of their families and localities because of actions associated with their drug use, even after rehabilitation. PWID, like MSM, said they faced insult and derision from community members with negative nicknames like 'Mateja' hurled towards them. PWID participants described not being trusted by clinic staff and clients who perceive them as 'thieves' or 'vagabonds'. They also stated that health care workers have not been sensitized on how to treat PWID. These perceptions and lack of sensitization often led to discrimination, especially at government hospitals. PWID also said they suffered discrimination within religious settings. Some described that they have been chased away from mosques and churches because they were labeled as thieves.

FSWs

FSWs described discrimination from different quarters due to the nature of their work. In general, they said they faced discrimination within the communities where they live and faced eviction from their homes and mistreatment by neighbors. Within the healthcare setting FSWs said they have been asked to bring their partners when they go to seek treatment, especially when presenting with STIs. As a result, they ended up not being served or forced to seek help elsewhere. FSWs are also discriminated at

places of worship. Known FSWs are denied leadership and opportunities in church along with being cast aside and called names.

MMs

Mature minors who are HIV positive described discrimination due to discrimination in school, in which they are required to use separate utensils. They also described feeling neglected at home and not being accepted by members of their community.

Influence of Religion on Stigma & Discrimination and Access to Health Services

Beliefs and Practices

Compassion

In describing factors that motivated their work with members of key populations, staff from FBOs mentioned lived experiences and religious and ethical obligations. A participant that worked with PWID detailed how the loss of a relative from addiction motivated him to work with people suffering from the same condition. Among participants who self-identify as a member of a key population, they empathize with the struggle and stigma key populations may encounter in seeking health care services. Other staff members spoke of their commitment to the Hippocratic Oath to serve all in need, and some alluded to religion by stating that by serving key populations (service to men) they were also serving God. In general, the staff members mentioned that their ability to either empathize or sympathize with members of key populations enables them to facilitate that key populations are happy, receiving health services, and are feeling welcomed and safe at their facilities. Furthermore, the FBO participants also explained that compassion helps them to understand what the key populations they serve are going through.

Participants stated that some FBOs were created out of compassion for key populations; the organizations hoped to improve the lives of their clients through their targeted, key population friendly services. To further that mission and reach a large portion of key populations, some FBOs do not charge for their services. Staff members described how compassion enables them to see key populations as ordinary people, human beings in need of assistance; for example, their perception that drug addiction is like any disease and so should be treated as such.

“First it’s because they are human beings, and this is an addiction. It’s a disease , so those they are the things that we normally care about , it’s a human being and we have seen him changed , he contributes positively to the community and that is why we give them more chances because you never know which chance will help him out”.

Male, PWID, 40, Muslim, Mombasa

Religious teachings related to key populations

A majority of the participants in the study professed to be religious, with a handful claiming to be atheists. Those who expressed that they were religious declared fidelity to Christianity and Islam despite perceived conflict between religious beliefs and homosexuality, sex work, and drug use. The participants explained that they attended places of worship regularly, prayed, and continued to read holy texts. With

the exception of PWID and mature minors, participants described the ways in which they reconciled religious teachings – often employed to stigmatize them – with their sexual orientation and profession.

MSM participants were insistent that beliefs and practices, especially in Christianity were not observed equally. One participant gave the example of a wedding ceremony that occurred in church for a woman who was pregnant, and the congregants refusal to address her sin – fornication. For MSM, they believed the church was obsessed with homosexuality as a sin and elevated it above all other vices. The participants were deeply troubled and resented this unfair treatment. Due to this treatment, those who still felt close to God opted to stay at home and pray on their own rather than attend church services. Others had turned to atheism to escape the endless scrutiny and condemnation present in Islam and Christianity.

FSWs often referenced the biblical exchange between Jesus and the Samaritan woman, who had “many men who were not her husband.” According to one FSW, the church should always pray for FSWs and understand their humanity, since it was the Samaritan, a sex worker who saved Jesus from death by giving him water. For other FSWs, the depiction of sex workers in religious text validates their profession and serves as encouragement.

Similar to the opinions expressed by FSWs and MSM, PWID believed that their relationship with drugs was definitely against their respective religions. Though currently unable to worship, they too, found the practice of religion to be important. Furthermore, unlike other key populations, most PWID thought religious institutions were more understanding of their plight.

“Even there are those who brought a prostitute before God, God told them if you know that you are not a sinner be the first to throw a stone so they all went away and left the woman alone. You will go to God and you will be forgiven.”

Female, SW, 33, Christian, Kiambu

On the other hand, MMs said they received strict teachings on alcohol and drugs, and if they were found to use drugs, religious leaders did not seek to understand why. They explained that they did not understand the beliefs prohibiting alcohol if Jesus turned water into wine and that they used drugs to handle stress or forget problems despite religious teachings.

Agency and Power

Double life

MSM, SWs, and PLWHIV frequently discussed the concept of living a double life. Informing neighbors and friends of jobs in faraway towns; marrying a person of a gender they are not attracted to; or refusing to seek services at health facilities are examples of the great lengths some participants took to hide their sexual orientation, profession, and HIV status.

Some MSM expressed that although they were exclusively attracted to men, they decided to marry women due to perceived pressure from their family and society. Others would conceal their sexual orientation by simultaneously dating men and women. In Kilifi and Mombasa, male sex workers (MSWs) with predominately male clientele, self-identified as heterosexuals and not gay or same gender loving.

In their profession as sex workers, both male and female participants, discussed religious leaders (Muslim and Christians) whose public stance on homosexuality and sex work contradicted their private

life. FSWs and MSWs described Christian leaders and pastors who were regular customers, yet these same individuals would preach against sex work every Sunday. According to participants, in order to avoid disclosure, Muslims leaders would take the additional step of approaching Christian or Atheist FSWs. In addition, FSWs claimed that there were women who were engaged in sex work and transactional sex within the church but did not self-identify as FSWs. The participants were stigmatized and discriminated against by the women who did not openly identifying as sex workers.

“As Sex workers, sometimes we get approached by top leaders in the church. When you are in church they ask for your number and at night they call you. In the morning they are in church but at night you meet even the Bishops and Fathers and they pay us.”

Female, SW, 40, Christian, Kisumu

The fear and apprehension participants mentioned about disclosing their sexual orientation and profession to families and friends, were also a factor in seeking services at health centers. MSM participants were afraid to disclose their sexual orientation to the health service providers for fear that it would make them vulnerable to stigma and discrimination. Although they try to avoid questions that could lead to this disclosure, sometimes it is unavoidable – for example, when seeking services for anal warts. They also believe the lack of confidentiality at health service centers would lead to community members being informed about their sexual orientation, profession, or HIV status.

“I am who I am”

MSM who self-identified as Christian, viewed the religious tenet of practicing love as confirmation that same gender loving relationships are allowable within Christianity. They also stated that their sexual orientation was in accordance with God’s image. If God created them in his own image and He makes no mistakes with his creations, therefore, being born as a same gender loving person, identifying, and living as such is in accordance with God’s wishes. Additionally, for some MSM, they identify themselves first as a Christian before MSM.

However, all members of key populations stated that they believed homosexuality, adultery, and drug use go against the tenets of Islam and Christianity. Participants also explained that every sin is equal before God, despite the community’s desires to elevate homosexuality and sex work above other sins. According to some participants, if homosexuality and sex work are viewed as a sin, it is no worse than the sins committed by others, such as tribalism and corruption.

In their discussion, some FSWs noted that they would repent to God for their profession and God was accepting of them. While some of the participants attempted to reconcile biblical teachings and sex work, others complained that religion was not making any effort to understand the plight of FSWs. As their only viable option to earn a living, most FSWs explained that they would eventually stop sex work with age or once they were able to find alternative forms of employment.

“It is within the church as an institution. It is the individuals who are discriminating. But the Church itself, the bible preaches love, the bible does not preach hate. The bible does not err...the bible says do not judge. So who are you to judge me? We are all the same before God. And every sin remember is the same before God. So the

church as it is very, very okay, but the individuals within the church are making it more complicated.”

Male, MSM, 23, Christian, Kisumu

Peer educators

Participants described the importance of peers in referring them to trusted health services. Peer educators were usually described as empowered members of various key populations who are trained and monitored by FBOs to liaise with other members of their communities. Peer educators would conduct outreach in localities that key populations frequented and connect them to health facilities.

Organizational Structure of Religious Communities

Relationship of the FBO to the religious structure

The perspective of the participants were that FBOs operate under strict adherence to religious doctrines and the policies of the “mother church.” Catholic FBOs followed Catholic rules and doctrines, while other FBOs (e.g. Anglican, Coptic, and Muslim) adhered to guidelines established by their respective religious bodies. This adherence to established religious doctrine and church policy has been credited with the attitude of FBOs towards key populations, especially MSM. The structures were blamed for the emphasis on salvation as opposed to service at FBOs where clients regularly complained of being preached to and condemned instead of being served without discrimination. However, participants also credited religious authorities and doctrines for inspiring the work FBOs conduct in communities.

“I think that one of the things we need to know is that faith based organizations, according to their doctrines, they don’t allow homosexuality. As per the bible and perception also so going against the bible or the Qur’an would be like preaching water then drinking wine. So for them also again they are looking at it in terms of, if they promote homosexuality, yet the bible is very clear about not accepting homosexuality, then they would be going against the bible and the Qur’an. So it’s about the issue of perception and also us as MSM we are not out...”

Male, MSM, 23, Christian, Kisumu

“Aaahhhhhhhh why are we not again targeting key population? I can say that each organization has its own principals its own ethics and we are an assumedly Christian organization and I can say that a lot affects our approach to service delivery particularly with the MSM and SWs aaaaaahhhhhhhh because on one way or another it is seen that their behavior probably is against the Christian teaching and aaaaaahhhhhh disciples of mercy is assumedly linked to the church therefore our services are based on the Christian principal . We use Christian resources to serve.”

Christian FBO in Kisumu

Neutrality in religious affiliation of the FBO

The participants were asked if they were inclined to seek services at certain FBOs due to religious affiliations and if they saw the staff demonstrate any religious beliefs. Most participants mentioned that their personal religious beliefs or that of a FBO does not dictate where they seek health services.

Participants highlighted Reach Out Kenya as a Muslim FBO that provides targeted services to PWID in Mombasa, yet services are geared towards all PWID regardless of the client's tribe and religious beliefs.

"You give the services and preaching is for somewhere else, this is a health facility, preaching is something else. So you just give services to the clients and if she /he feels to go mosque or church that is for them to decide, we offer services to them."

Male, MSM, 28, Christian, Kilifi

Key populations described that services at most organizations are offered to all without considering if a client is a Muslim or Christian. However, a pair of participants in Mombasa expressed that within Muslim FBOs, staff showed preference to clients who wore a "the Hijab, . FBO observed that they focused on providing services to meet client needs as opposed to identifying with religious affiliations. Participants from both key population groups and FBOs expressed that sometimes staff at FBOs may mention religious beliefs or doctrines when providing care, and sensitization is important for FBO staff.

"So in an attempt to open their HIV prevention services the next thing you know is can you be born again? A client might not be going for salvation, a client might be going for treatment."

Christian FBO in Kisumu

Targeted support for key populations

Due to donor requirements, program design or organizational mission, some FBOs have to prioritize which key populations they will work with and how to provide them with certain health services. According to participants, most FBOs target one specific key population, although there are a few that provide services to both MSM and FSWs. There are unique organizations, such as Hope Worldwide Kenya that serve PWID, FSWs, and MSM. Notably, certain FBOs limit not only who they serve, but also the type of services they can provide. Participants cited FBOs that many can only test for HIV and then refer them to other facilities, whereas, others only provide antiretroviral drugs. However, one FBO shared that they were able to provide comprehensive services to MSM while other FBOs were limited in the scope of services. Despite some of these shortcomings, participants felt that FBOs were friendly and sympathetic towards key populations.

"Adding to what [the other participant] has said, when you go to ICRH...at the beginning they were serving Female Sex Workers only. But now they have discovered...they have another program for mothers. I you go to ICRH you will find a department that serves female sex workers and also mothers..."

Female, SW, 20, Muslim, Kilifi

"In this area [Uasin Gishu], I feel we provide services to the key populations. We have another organization [...] they just provide trainings for their MSM, they provide condoms and lubricants. They don't test they don't give clinical services. We feel that our services are comprehensive because when a client comes in here being tested being given family planning services, STI treatment and ART services we feel that our services are comprehensive."

Challenges in serving key populations

FBOs personnel underscored numerous challenges they face in providing health services to key populations, including their inability to offer one-stop shop services to key populations. As it was previously noted, members of key populations receive specific targeted health services at FBOs, a problem the FBOs recognize but are unable to resolve. Both FBO and key population participants expressed that many FBOs do not have the capacity, in staff or medical and laboratory resources to address the spectrum of medical needs of key populations. As a result, FBOs often refer key populations to government health facilities, where they fear their clients will face stigma and discrimination.

“They offer good services but they lack facilities and they only have first aid kits, they give condoms, Syringes, food advice. It’s like a first aid service, one cannot sleep. One cannot sleep, transfuse blood so it’s a small facility.”

Female, PWID, 24, Muslim, Kilifi

According to FBO participants, organizations face threats from surrounding communities, because they serve key populations. This was a common challenge across all regions, but it was especially a concern in Mombasa. The participants in Mombasa stated members of the Muslim community plot attacks and shut down organizations serving key populations. In order to safeguard themselves from this threat, organizations serving key populations hide their true purpose, and in some instances, do not serve surrounding communities. Consequentially, key populations from the local community seeking services from these organizations are often referred to other facilities or turned away.

In addition, participants said that FBOs face high staff turnover due to funding challenges and the short-term contracts they offer employees. Furthermore, heavy reliance on temporary donor funds hinders FBOs the reach and efficacy in serving key populations. The funding challenges limit their service offerings and organizations must address unrealistic expectation from key populations who expect more than the FBOs have to offer. While FBOs often provide free services and other benefits, participants across the board expressed that FBOs should offer more services. FBOs also hold sensitization training for health care workers at government and private health facilities where they normally refer their clients. Sometimes these trainings do not work and clients return with claims of stigma and discrimination that the sensitization was meant to curb. Another key challenge is the criminalization of sex work and MSM. FSWs and MSM are harassed and mistreated by the authorities and the society due to homosexuality and sex work being illegal. This hampers the organizations’ ability to serve their clients and lobby for their rights.

Sex work being illegal in Kenya. Another challenge is that we want to make sure that all the sex workers report their cases so we are trying to do the decriminalization of sex workers so that when we are doing the decriminalization we will have a lot of evidence. Sometimes the sex workers are raped and violated and they fear reporting. Now we are doing some training to the sex worker community whereby we are explaining to them why we want the decriminalization instead of the legal process, why this criminal laws affects us, why they should be reporting and have evidence.”

Male, Sex Worker, 42, Christian, Kiambu

Relationship of Religion to Broader society

How key populations perceive religion in relation to broader society

Religion was described by some as an important moral guide for individuals or the community. Some expressed the ways that religion sets rules or “do’s and don’ts” based on doctrinal texts, even if not all individuals follow those rules. For example, religion may set rules for contraceptive use, but it will not be followed by a religious couple who cannot afford to have multiple children or by a sex worker who protects his/herself with a condom.

“You ignore it because there is faith and wisdom and both go hand in hand. Even though I apply faith and I have someone and I avoid using contraceptives I will end up being pregnant and the church will not be there. The pastor gives you the word but the choice is yours, he can’t give you the word opposite of the bible teachings.”

Female, Sex Worker, 28, Christian, Kiambu

While some described these rules as helpful for individuals and society, others found them to be rigid, hypocritical, or lacking understanding for human needs. In particular, PWID and MMs explained instances of introducing health information or programs (e.g., needle exchange, sex education) into religious settings, but not always being accepted.

“Because you know, I tried creating that information-based...place. The way we've been taught here [at the FBO]. Like information is just there, you are free and all that. I tried to create that in church, where people can be free to talk about anything, as long as it's youth based. But the response was not good because some of them were not comfortable with it. “

Female, MM, Christian, 14, Kiambu

MMs, MSM and SWs described the role of religion in relation to national laws in which religion shapes laws in the country (e.g. teaching condom use in high school, needle exchange policies), but also must abide by the law. For example, one participant said health is a human right guaranteed by the constitution but not always adhered to in health settings, where religious belief may influence discrimination against MSM. On the other hand, FBOs may find a way to provide services directly to sex workers who may otherwise face challenges accessing services in public facilities that require patients to bring a partner for sexual health consultations. Key populations may seek out services at FBOs that give them psychosocial support, even if those services are not supported by the wider religious community or community at large.

“We are given food, free lunch, there was a time that this was stage outside, we would go and eat there, but later there erupted politics, actually this politics emanated from Muslim elders who claimed that Mewa was giving food to clients so that they could regain their energy for them to be able to steal from us and those are Muslims talk like that about this organization which is Islamic”

Male, PWID, Muslim, 28, Kilifi

Relationships between FBOs and wider society

FBO participants described a range of relationships with wider society, including private or public funders, partnerships with civil society and government, and targeted peer outreach to key populations. They also described their role as FBOs in relation to broader cultural norms and laws.

Among the FBO participants interviewed, some described the importance of relationships with funders from the private and public sector to support health service provision. These relationships often drove the services that the FBO was able to provide and whether or not an FBO served key populations. Gaps in funding, or a lack of funding to target key populations limited the scope of services that the FBO could provide. Therefore, FBOs often developed and relied up partnerships with other FBOs and NGOs. These partnerships included linkage to services, sharing of resources and facilities, and trainings. For example, organizations with the training expertise and resources would train partner staff on different aspects of providing efficient health services to members of key populations. Some trainings were also provided by government agencies to improve quality of clinical services.

Participants also discussed the concept of FBOs working under an umbrella body. This usually encompasses different organizations coming together under a single body in order to effect change or combine efforts towards a common goal. Partnership also took place between organizations and government agencies or structures like the National Aids Control Council and County Aids Steering Committees.

“Okay, at the local level, through this member bodies of GALCK that we are able to reach out to now the people on the grassroots. Like for instance, [church], being a member of GALCK, is able to reach out to other local churches, involving pastors and other local groups, which now [the church] acts as a link between GALCK and the local community. So if there is any information coming from GALCK, which is the umbrella body, to this other/maybe to the wider society to use the/its member bodies to communicate or rather to pass information or to link up with the society. And then GALCK, being the umbrella body now, it represents this other organizations in government agencies. Like for instance the Ministry of Health. You know, it has partnered with ISHTAR, with HOYMAS and all that, through GALCK.”

Male, MSM, 25, Christian, Nairobi

FBOs also had differing relationships with key populations. Some FBOs provide services to the “general population”, which sometimes include key populations. However, they do not intentionally target them. Others target only a specific key population (e.g. MSM) and refer all others to NGOs or FBOs that can meet their needs. For example, Tamba Pwani, an FBO that exclusively serves MSM, often receives FSWs that are seeking care at their facility, instead of refusing to see them, they refer all sex workers to partner organizations that are better equipped to serve sex workers. Sometimes government health facilities would referred PWID to Reach Out Kenya, an FBO that could conduct assessments and enroll them in their methadone program. On the other hand, one FBO participant interviewed described that they specifically target all key populations (PWID, MMs, MSM, SWs) and refer members of the general population for follow up care at public facilities. To reach these key populations, this FBO has peer outreach staff at “hotspots” where MSM or SWs are known to frequent to encourage HIV testing. Key

population participants in other counties reinforced that FBOs work through peer educators to reach them.

“Through our peer educators, I came to know about [the FBO]. Because in every Hotspot we have peer educators that are working with [the FBO]. So they are the people who are always reaching us.”

Female, Sex Worker, 38, Christian, Kisumu

Discussion

Interpretation of findings, recommendations, future action

